

Statistical Analysis Plan

Respiratory related signals in EEG

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This document serves to preregister the statistical analysis plan of my Master thesis project titled “Respiratory related signals in EEG” which I am conducting at the Translational Neuromodeling Unit (TNU). The goal of this project is to quantify electroencephalography (EEG) responses to natural, unrestricted breathing, or more specifically, to discover and characterize EEG responses that are linked to particular periods of the (physiological) breathing cycle. The characterization of such EEG responses (if present) is a foundation for future experiments in which breathing will be modified to explore interoceptive processing.

The current document is the second part of the analysis plan of the project. For a description of the data set, and how it will be preprocessed, see the separate file containing the first part of the analysis plan¹.

Analysis

As described in the first part of the analysis plan, the data set analyzed in this project includes the EEG and breathing belt data of 41 healthy male participants which were collected for a previously published study by Petzschner et al. [1]. These data were recorded both in a "resting state" as well as for a set of tasks, leading to a total of 287 EEG runs (1 resting state run and 6 task-based runs per participant) with a recording length between 8 and 21 minutes.

Of the 41 total participants, 10 participants (with all 7 runs) were randomly chosen for a discovery subset on which exploratory analysis was conducted. The findings from that exploratory analysis guide the future analysis described here, which will be performed on the validation subset comprised of the remaining 31 participants.

Please note that at the time of writing this document, the validation data have not yet been statistically analyzed.

Prior to statistical analysis, both the EEG data and breathing belt data are preprocessed and the data quality checked, according to the steps outlined in the first part of the analysis plan. Furthermore, the respiratory phase is extracted from the breathing belt data in order to be used in statistical analyses of its correlation with the EEG data.

All statistical analyses will be computed using MATLAB² and SPM12.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/12795124>

² Version 24.1.0.2653294 (R2024a) Update 5

Event-related potential approach

Previous studies have found respiratory-related evoked potentials (RREP), but only for restricted breathing [2], [3]. The first hypothesis which was explored on the discovery subset was that such a RREP also exists for natural unrestricted breathing. As the definition of a temporal onset for an evoked potential is ambiguous for natural breathing, possible evoked potentials were systematically analyzed for different onsets during the respiratory cycle.

However, this ERP approach led to no clear results in our discovery dataset and will not be pursued further in my thesis project. Therefore, it is not described here in more detail and will not be applied to the validation set.

Time-frequency based analysis

Various past studies have found breathing-EEG correlates with time-frequency based approaches, though the reported results differ. Zelano et al. [4] found low-frequency alignment of the local field potential (LFP) with the respiratory cycle in the human piriform cortex, as well as an inspiration-locked increase in oscillatory power in the delta, theta, and beta bands in limbic-related brain areas. Herrero et al. [5] also found phase-amplitude coupling between respiration and neural oscillations in cortical and limbic areas. However, the power increases were observed in the gamma band and during the beginning and end of exhalation. While these studies focused on natural breathing, they used intracranial EEG (iEEG). A non-invasive EEG study by Schreiner et al. [6] reports phase-amplitude coupling in the delta, theta and beta bands at frontal, central and parietal electrodes. Though because this study focused on sleep oscillations, it did not examine higher frequency bands, and the sleep EEG recordings may differ from the awake state. Taken together, these findings motivate the second hypothesis to be explored in non-invasive, awake-state EEG recordings: Are there power fluctuations in specific EEG frequency bands that are tightly coupled to the breathing cycle?

To explore this second hypothesis, the following procedure will be used on the validation set: First, the preprocessed EEG signal of each run will be band-pass filtered into six different frequency bands using a two pass Butterworth filter (fourth order). The cut-off frequencies are defined such that the filter response overlaps as seamlessly as possible³:

- Delta band: 1 Hz – 4.5 Hz
 - o The threshold for the delta band is chosen above 1Hz to exclude any signals which may be in-phase with breathing as we are interested particularly in an EEG response which varies over the course of the respiratory cycle.
- Theta band: 3.5 Hz – 8.5 Hz
- Alpha band: 7.5 Hz – 15 Hz
- Beta band: 13 Hz – 31 Hz
- Low gamma band: 29 Hz – 67 Hz
- High gamma band: 63 Hz – 100 Hz

For each of these filtered traces, the measured EEG activity $E(t)$ will be decomposed into an instantaneous activity $E_a(t)$ and an instantaneous phase signal $\varphi(t)$ using the Hilbert transform:

$$E(t) = E_a(t) \cos(\varphi(t)).$$

³ This was evaluated on the discovery set

To compute the power, the absolute value of the instantaneous activity will be squared:

$$P(t) = |E_a(t)|^2$$

Next, the phase of each respiratory cycle will be divided into 100 equally spaced phase points $\phi_i \in [0, 2\pi)$ and the power will be extracted at the corresponding timepoints t_i such that $\phi(t_i) = \phi(i)$. This will lead to a separate power signal for each run, frequency band and EEG channel, which will be sampled 100 times per respiratory cycle. To make the power comparable across frequency bands and to limit the effect of potential outliers, it will be log-normalized and z-scored: First, the logarithm of the power will be computed and second, the log-power will be z-scored. This means that for each EEG channel, the data will be rescaled so that it has a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. Note that the median absolute deviation (MAD), a robust estimator of the standard deviation, will be used to avoid impact of potential outliers on the estimation of the variance. After normalization, the power signal will be averaged first over respiratory cycles, then over runs. The normalized power signal for each frequency band can then be visualized in relation to the respiratory phase, either for distinct respiratory bands or as a grand channel average.

To quantify the coupling between the respiratory phase and the power amplitude (averaged across EEG channels), a modulation index (MI) will be computed. This measure was developed by Tort et al. [7] to study cross-frequency couplings and has been used in previous studies on breathing-EEG correlates [4], [6]. It will be adopted here in a simplified way: First, the phase will be binned into 20 intervals (from originally 100 phase points) and the normalized power signal will be averaged over each of these bins. Then the modulation index will be computed as:

$$MI = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N |p_j - \bar{p}|,$$

where $N = 20$ is the number of bins, p_j is the normalized power averaged over the bin j and \bar{p} is the normalized power averaged over the entire respiratory cycle. This thus corresponds to the absolute difference between the normalized power and the uniform distribution.

In order to examine the statistical significance of the MI, a distribution of surrogate MI will be created. To achieve this, the normalized power signal will be randomly shifted over the respiratory phase for each respiratory cycle separately, using concatenation along the edges. This process will be repeated 200 times to create the distribution of surrogate MI. The significance threshold $p = 0.05$ will be controlled for multiple comparisons across the six frequency bands using Bonferroni correction. The significance threshold is thus determined as the 99.16th percentile of the surrogate distribution.

In the analysis of the discovery set it was found that the resting state runs and task-based runs showed differences in the relationship between the respiratory phase and the power amplitude. While for the resting state runs, there was a significant phase-amplitude coupling between breath and power only in the high gamma band, in the task-based runs there was a significant coupling for the alpha, beta, and both gamma bands. However, it is noteworthy that the phase-amplitude coupling in the theta band of the resting state runs was visually most clear and most consistent across runs, though its modulation index was not significant. We hypothesize that on the validation set, the same bands will have significant phase-amplitude couplings within the task-based subset and the resting-based subset, respectively, and that additionally, the resting-based subset will have significant phase-amplitude coupling in the theta band.

To evaluate not only whether the respiratory phase modulates the EEG power amplitude, but also at which point in the respiratory cycle the power is modulated, we will compute one-sample t-tests at each sampled normalized power value. The t-test will be performed only in bands which were found to have a significant MI. P-values will be corrected to control for false discovery rate (FDR) over

the 100 power samples of the respiratory cycle using a Benjamini-Hochberg procedure with an alpha-value of 0.05.

Finally, we want to evaluate whether the spatial topography of the power modulation is consistent between the discovery set and the validation set. To examine this, a principal component analysis (computed using a singular value decomposition) is performed on the normalized power-over-respiratory-phase trace in EEG channel space. The spatial components are in the shape of a vector in EEG channel space which points in the direction of the maximum variance of the power modulation. The vector weights can be plotted on the scalp map to visualize and qualitatively compare the topography between discovery and validation set, both in the resting state and task-based runs.

References

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